

AMINO DERIVATIVES OF TITANIUM TETRABROMIDE. PART IV

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The amino derivatives of titanium tetrabromide have been prepared by the action of titanium tetrabromide on some aliphatic and aromatic amines, and their properties studied.

In earlier communications of the series (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 838; 1957, 34, 452), the action of titanium tetrabromide on some amines and heterocyclic bases was studied. The work has now been extended to the study of the effect of some less common amines having one or more :NH or :N groups on anhydrous titanic bromide.

EXPERIMENTAL

The amines used were of Merck's or B.D.H.'s 'extra pure' quality. Titanium tetrabromide was prepared by the method of Olsen and Ryan (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 2215), redistilled at 230° and extracted with anhydrous ether, distilled over sodium metal.

General Method of Preparation.—The compounds were prepared by adding slowly a dilute ethereal solution of titanic bromide to amine solution in ether with constant shaking. However, if the process be reversed, a sticky mass is generally obtained which is not easily converted into a pure crystalline precipitate. The precipitate formed was stirred well with a slight excess of the amine solution and kept for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour in a dry atmosphere; it was filtered and washed with ether till free of the amine. It was dried over anhydrous calcium chloride, analysed and the properties studied. In the compounds: *tetrakis-n*-butylanilino-, *-n*-propylanilino-, *iso*-amylanilino-, *-dimethyl-o*-toluidino-, *-diethyl-o*-toluidino-, *-dimethyl-p*-toluidino-, and *diethyl-p*-toluidino-titanic bromides, the amines were also estimated by the potentiometric method. Duplicate titrations were carried out. The results recorded in Table II are the averages of the two values.

Estimation of Amine.—The compound (~0.2-0.8 g.) was weighed out accurately, treated with HCl (50 c.c., conc.) and the volume made up to 250 c.c. An aliquot of the solution (25 c.c.) was pipetted out in an iodine flask and 15 c.c. each of *M*/₂-KBr and 0.1*N*-KBrO₃ added to it. It was kept for a definite period of time (vide Table I) and 15 c.c. of 0.1*N*-As₂O₃ added to it. The mixture was shaken well, filtered in case any precipitate or turbidity appeared, and titrated back with KBrO₃ at the room temperature. The curves (vol. of KBrO₃ in c.c. against $\Delta E/\Delta V$) were drawn and from the amount of bromine consumed, the quantity of amine and the percentage of nitrogen in the compounds calculated.

The blank titrations were carried out with each amine under identical conditions. Only the curves for *iso*amylaniline and *diethyl-p*-toluidine (Fig. 1, curves I & II) have been shown.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The curves III-V in Fig. 1 and VI-IX in Fig. 2 refer to the estimation of amine in *tetrakis*-diethyl-*o*-toluidino-, -dimethyl-*p*-toluidino-, -diethyl-*p*-toluidino-, -*n*-propylanilino-, -*n*-butylanilino-, *iso*amylanilino-, and dimethyl-*o*-toluidino-titanic bromide respectively.

TABLE I

Amines.	Wt. in 100 c.c.	Bromination period.	Bromine consumed.
<i>n</i> -Propylaniline	0.3378 g.	2-5 mins.	3Br ₂
<i>n</i> -Butylaniline	0.1756	"	3Br ₂
<i>iso</i> Amylaniline	0.1838	"	3Br ₂
Dimethyl- <i>o</i> -toluidine	0.1734	25-30	2Br ₂
Diethyl- <i>o</i> - "	0.2026	"	1Br ₂
Dimethyl- <i>p</i> - "	0.4482	"	1Br ₂
Diethyl- <i>p</i> - "	0.5118	"	1Br ₂

TABLE II*

Compounds.	Wt. of the compound.	Wt. of the amine. Calc.	Found (from the curve).	% Nitrogen.
<i>iso</i> Amylaniline	0.1838 g.	0.1838 g.	0.1840 g.	8.60
Diethyl- <i>o</i> -toluidine	0.2026	0.2026	0.2011	8.52
<i>t</i> - <i>n</i> -Propylanilino-T.B.	0.4318	0.2568	0.2558	6.17
<i>t</i> - <i>n</i> -Butylanilino-T.B.	0.3914	0.2420	0.2406	5.78
<i>t</i> - <i>iso</i> Amylanilino-T.B.	0.3196	0.2043	0.2033	5.46
<i>t</i> -Dimethyl- <i>o</i> -toluidino-T.B.	0.7698	0.4578	0.4566	6.15
<i>t</i> -Diethyl- <i>o</i> - "	0.4604	0.2943	0.2931	5.47
<i>t</i> -Dimethyl- <i>p</i> - "	0.8206	0.4880	0.4909	6.20
<i>t</i> -Diethyl- <i>p</i> - "	0.5968	0.3815	0.3829	5.51

* *t* denotes tetrakis.

T.B. denotes tetranitricbromide.

TABLE III

Compounds of titanium tetrabromide with secondary amines.

Amine.	Compound formed.	Colour.	M.P.	% Titanium.		% Bromine.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
<i>n</i> -Propyl- aniline	<i>t</i> - <i>n</i> -Propylanilino-T.B. [Ti(C ₆ H ₅ -NHC ₃ H ₇) ₄]Br ₄	Brownish grey	108°	5.32	5.29	35.06	35.24	6.12	6.19
<i>n</i> -Butyl- aniline	<i>t</i> - <i>n</i> -Butylanilino-T.B. [Ti(C ₆ H ₅ NH.C ₄ H ₉) ₄]Br ₄	White with greyish shade	97°	5.01	4.99	33.18	33.20	5.76	5.81
<i>iso</i> Amyl- aniline	<i>t</i> - <i>iso</i> Amylanilino-T.B. [Ti { C ₆ H ₅ NH.C ₅ H ₅ (CH ₃) ₂ } ₄]Br ₄	Dirty white	144°	4.70	4.71	31.26	31.37	5.42	5.49
Dibenzyl- amine	<i>t</i> -Dibenzylamino-T.B. [Ti { (C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂) ₂ NH } ₄]Br ₄	White	...	4.11	4.15	27.58	27.68	4.80	4.84
Di- <i>p</i> -tolyl- amine	<i>t</i> -Di- <i>p</i> -tolylamino-T.B. [Ti { (CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄) ₂ NH } ₄]Br ₄	Greyish white	182-83°	4.17	4.15	27.54	27.68	4.78	4.84
Di- <i>n</i> -propyl- amine	<i>t</i> -Di- <i>n</i> -propylanilino-T.B. (Ti { (C ₃ H ₇) ₂ NH } ₄)Br ₄	White	320°	6.20	6.22	41.37	41.45	7.16	7.25
Dimethyl- <i>p</i> -pheny- lene- diamine	<i>bis</i> -Dimethyl- <i>p</i> - phenylene-diamino-T.B. [Ti { C ₆ H ₄ (NH.CH ₃) ₂ } ₄]Br ₄	Dark ash	...	7.52	7.50	49.8	50.00	8.68	8.75

TABLE IV

Compounds of titanium tetrabromide with tertiary amines.

Amine.	Compound formed.	Colour.	M.P.	% Titanium.		% Bromine.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Dimethyl- <i>o</i> -toluidine	<i>t</i> -Dimethyl- <i>o</i> -toluidino-T.B. [Ti { CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₃) ₂ } ₄]Br ₄	Pinkish grey	86°	5.26	5.29	35.08	35.24	6.12	6.19
Diethyl- <i>o</i> -toluidine	<i>t</i> -Diethyl- <i>o</i> -toluidino-T.B. [Ti { CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ } ₄]Br ₄	Greyish white	90°	4.72	4.71	31.24	31.37	5.42	5.49
Dimethyl- <i>p</i> -toluidine	<i>t</i> -Dimethyl- <i>p</i> -toluidino-T.B. [Ti { CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₃) ₂ } ₄]Br ₄	Yellow	78°	5.28	5.29	35.06	35.24	6.10	6.19
Diethyl- <i>p</i> -toluidine	<i>t</i> -Diethyl- <i>p</i> -toluidino-T.B. [Ti { CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ } ₄]Br ₄	Dirty white	156°	4.69	4.71	31.28	31.37	5.44	5.49
Triethyl- amine	<i>t</i> -Triethylamino-T.B. [Ti { (C ₂ H ₅) ₃ N } ₄]Br ₄	„	309-10°	6.24	6.22	41.36	41.45	7.18	7.25
γ -Picoline	<i>t</i> - γ -Picolino-T.B. [Ti(CH ₃ .C ₅ H ₄ .N) ₄]Br ₄	White	212°	6.25	6.49	43.06	43.24	7.48	7.57
Tribenzyl- amine	<i>t</i> -Tribenzylamino-T.B. [Ti { (C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂) ₃ N } ₄]Br ₄	„	214°	3.19	3.17	21.06	21.11	3.65	3.69
<i>pp'</i> -Tetra- methyl- diamino- benzophe- none.	<i>bis</i> - <i>pp'</i> -Tetramethyl- diaminobenzophenone-T.B. [Ti { (CH ₃) ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ CO } ₂]Br ₄	Orange- yellow	...	5.22	5.31	34.68	35.40	6.04	6.19

* Slightly low values were obtained as the compound was very hygroscopic in nature.

The compounds are insoluble in common organic solvents and are similar to the amino derivatives of titanium tetrabromide of the previous series. *tetrakis*-Dimethyl-*p*-toluidino-, -di-*n*-propylamino-, -di-*p*-tolylamino-, -triethylamino-, - γ -picolino-, and *bis-pp'*-tetramethyldiaminobenzophenone-titanic bromides are readily soluble in dilute mineral acids and the rest are insoluble. These hydrolyse slowly with cold water but readily with alkalis, and $Ti(OH)_4$ is precipitated according to the equation :

(where A stands for the amine).

On heating with sodalime, the corresponding amine separates out like the other amino derivatives of the series. The compounds formed with tertiary amines are not so stable as those formed with primary or secondary amines. The compound, *bis-pp'*-tetramethyldiaminobenzophenone-titanic bromide, where the co-ordination through two tertiary nitrogen takes place, is extremely hygroscopic and decomposes when exposed to atmosphere. The compound, *bis*-dimethyl-*p*-phenylenediamino-titanic bromide, like the primary diamino derivatives, as shown in Part I (*loc. cit.*), is very stable. The stability may likewise be attributed to the formation of the chelate compound.

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